

ABOUT THE CONTRIBUTION OF LIVESTOCK OF SURKHAN OASIS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TRADE AND THEIR TYPE

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ABSTRACT

This article talks about the development of cattle breeding in the Surkhan oasis after the establishment of Soviet power and the role of traders. During this period, he also researches the types of sheep distributed in the Surkhan region and what purpose they specialize in.

Thanks to independence, the lifestyle of our people has improved, and important work is being done to meet the needs of the population. It should be noted that important works are being carried out according to the socio-economic development program of Surkhandarya region of June 20, 2008 of the governor of the region. The most important thing is that the program to grow the regional economy at a stable high rate, as well as to ensure a 1.7-fold increase in gross regional products, is actually fulfilling the needs of the population in the market economy. The issue of creating favorable conditions for the use of opportunities for the labor force in the region, for the expansion of business initiatives in the field of services and services, especially in rural areas, created conditions for the use of new opportunities. Also, in order to satisfy the demand and needs of our people for livestock products, the issue of economic support of private and private livestock farms, creation of necessary conditions for them, timely delivery of fodder products for livestock was specially noted. Based on this, great opportunities were created for the residents of the city in the issue of production of livestock products and its establishment. By January 1, 2010, there were 49,280 head of cattle in our region, including 19,400 cows, 263,816 sheep and goats, and 244,600 poultry. Special achievements were made in the livestock sector, and 104,704 tons of meat were supplied to the market. delivered. It should be noted that animal husbandry is one of the oldest forms of traditional economic activities and one of the types of work that determine the factors of livelihood. In the oldest book "Avesta" special attention was paid to horses, cattle and domestic animals with small hooves. Even, "When asked where is the fourth place in the world that is happier than Hammam: such a place is answered that it is the land where a flock of sheep and a herd of camels are most cared for." In "Avesta" the return of cattle in herds is considered a holiday, and traditions related to cattle breeding have been passed down from centuries to centuries. Various rituals were performed to protect livestock from various diseases,

pestilence, wild beasts and thieves. The new year for cattle breeders starts on March 16, and the holiday is welcomed with the growth of grass.

It is known that two types of sheep are bred in the Surkhan oasis. These are Karakol (sheep breeding for the production of Karakol skins) and humped sheep. In Surkhandarya, humpbacked sheep breeding is widespread, and there are the following types: Kozhiki, Joydori, (Kazakh and Hisori sheep crossbreed), Hisori. Hisori sheep are mainly raised in Denov and Boysun districts. Depending on their natural conditions and use, pastures are divided into the following types: mountainside and desert pastures, i.e., autumn-winter-spring pastures in the submountain and desert regions, spring-summer pastures in the middle mountain regions, and summer pastures in the upper mountain regions.

In the foothills of Denov, Sherabad, and Boysun districts, the hisori cattle, which produce the most fat and meat, are raised and driven to the mountain areas in the summer months. The wool of these sheep was rough. Other types of sheep are raised in the Sherabad region, and these sheep are: Isliqi Karakoy (its size is smaller than Karakoy, the wool is softer, it is also called Kazakh sheep, Galjaki (crossed from the territory of Afghanistan), Chibalang (Arabic, Karakol), Korgoza (crossed from Kazakh and Chibalang). and sarjiparang (created by Sarjiboy) are divided into types. The shepherd and his shepherd were able to distinguish all the sheep in the flock (each flock has 1000-1500 sheep) regardless of their similarity, and if there was no sheep or lamb in the flock, he immediately noticed it and said that there was no sheep by color (color). told. Also, shepherds and our ancestors in general named sheep and lambs according to their age. A lamb is identified by traditional names, and after becoming a sheep, it is identified by its teeth. For example, a new-born lamb is called a lamb, a 2-3-month-old lamb is called a shirvaz lamb, a 4-5-month-old lamb is called a palace lamb, an older one is called a gaba lamb, a one-year-old lamb, a two-year-old shishak, a three-year-old chori, a four-year-old panji, a five-year-old lamb and so on. the older one was called mangi. It was mainly determined by the teeth, and the lamb's teeth remained in place until the sheep became scaly. After hatching, the middle two teeth fell out and big teeth grew in their place, when they got to the middle, they had 4 big teeth, and when they were sheep paws, all the front teeth turned into big teeth. In the years of independence, the attitude towards livestock was strengthened with great results, and a number of activities and programs were developed for the development of livestock, one of which is related to the issue of livestock breeding in the city.

Legal organization of tax opportunities for families dealing with livestock in the city, timely delivery of necessary fodder, and organization of veterinary services were noted as important issues. Also, breeding black cattle, meat-providing Hisar sheep, paying special attention to poultry farming, and using experienced scientific research sources qualified in their artificial insemination were put on the agenda. In particular, the issue of increasing the number of livestock, creating veterinary methodical manuals for the care of meat and milk breeds, and conducting propaganda work on the use of the work of experienced livestock farms was assigned. On this basis, excellent works are being carried out in the city of Termiz to feed livestock, provide the population with meat and milk, pay attention to poultry farming, and prevent the shortage of meat.

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